

An Open Source, Parallel, and Distributed Web-Based Probabilistic Risk Assessment Platform to Support Real Time Nuclear Power Plant Risk-Informed Operational Decisions

Milestone Report

Task 2: Design and Implementation

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Executive Summary

This milestone report builds on the findings from the first milestone, exploring the design phase of the project. In developing the framework, we leveraged open-source technologies and modern architectures. Additionally, a demonstration was conducted using basic events with higher probabilities, offering insights into multi-hazard models and highlighting the importance of accounting for quantification uncertainty when exact solutions are not feasible. As a follow-up, we introduce a quantification engine-agnostic PRA model pre-processor to efficiently handle the quantification of multi-hazard models.

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Disclaimer

The content of this report is largely a combination of various project outcomes, including conference papers, a master's thesis, and a Ph.D. dissertation.

Outcomes of the Project

The project contributes to the research environment in various ways, and the outcomes are listed below for reference. In addition to the listed outcomes, two journal papers are ready for submission, and one report covering the SAPHIRE post-processing engine is under review. Furthermore, North Carolina State University and Idaho National Laboratory have established a highly efficient collaborative environment.

1.1 Conference Papers

1. Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models [1]
2. Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM [2]
3. Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models [3]
4. Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment [4]
5. Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX [5]
6. Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement [6]
7. Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts [7]
8. Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence [8]
9. Towards a Deep-Learning Based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis [9]

1.2 Journal Papers

1. A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants [10]

1.3 Reports

1. Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver [11]

1.4 Master's Thesis

1. Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHSOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM [12]

1.5 Ph.D. Dissertation

1. Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Optimization and Parallel Computing [13]

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
BDD	Binary Decision Diagram
CLI	Command Line Interface
ESD	Event Sequence Diagram
HRA	Human Reliability Analysis
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWS	JSON Web Token
MCUB	Min Cut Upper Bound
MLD	Master Logic Diagram
REA	Rare Event Approximation
SQL	Structured Query Language
UI	User Interface
XML	Extensible Markup Language
ZBDD	Zero-Suppressed Binary Decision Diagram

1 Design and Implementation

1.1 Overview of Report

This report marks a significant milestone in the overall project. As a reminder, the project consists of five main tasks outlined below. This milestone report presents the outcomes of the first task:

- Task 1: Literature review, benchmarking, and profiling of current PRA tools
- Task 2: Design and implementation
- Task 3: Testing and benchmarking for serial and parallel improvements
- Task 4: Application to real-world PRA models
- Task 5: Verification and documentation

The remainder of the report is structured as follows: Section 1.2 details the REST API, while Section 1.3 introduces heuristics for model-specific optimization. Section 1.4 summarizes the parallel and distributed web-based architecture, and Section 1.5 demonstrates models that include basic events with higher probabilities, as seen in multi-hazard scenarios. Also, we introduce a quantification engine-agnostic PRA model pre-processor to efficiently handle the quantification of multi-hazard models. The report is concluded in Section 1.6.

1.2 REST APIs for Open-PSA Models

1.2.1 Design Choice

The backend of the OpenPRA platform is developed using the NestJS [14] framework, which is known for its structured, modular, and scalable architecture. NestJS promotes organized and reusable code through using decorators, facilitates TypeScript [15] support for enhanced type safety, includes built-in support for testing suites like Jest, and easily integrates with various structured query language (SQL) and non-SQL (NoSQL) databases. Additionally, NestJS is designed for high scalability, leveraging event-driven architecture and reactive programming to efficiently handle large number of concurrent requests, while seamlessly integrating with tools like GraphQL [16] and RabbitMQ [17] for real-time application development.

1.2.2 Basic Concepts

Before diving deeper into the backend structure, it is essential to understand the four fundamental components of NestJS: module, controller, service, and dependency injection.

Module helps to divide a NestJS application into logical units. Each module encapsulates individual controllers, services, and other necessary dependencies. A module acts as a boundary for dependency injection system and keeps the codebase modular and maintainable. The controller is responsible for handling incoming Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) requests from the client and returning responses either in the form of a JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) object or a standard HTTP status. Each controller method manages a specific route and a unique HTTP method, invoking the appropriate services to execute business logic. The service is the building block of a module. It implements business logic, interacts with the database or any other external service. A service can be injected into separate modules since it is loosely coupled and modular in nature. Dependency injection is a technique that allows a program to provide a class with its required dependencies from the outside, making the dependencies more flexible, reusable, and easier to test and maintain.

1.2.3 Backend Architecture

The core of the backend is encapsulated within the Application Programming Interface (API) module as shown in Figure 1. The backend application is initialized through loading this API module inside the bootstrap function and subsequently executing it. The API module serves as the main entry point for all the incoming HTTP requests. This module imports various other modules, each responsible for certain functionalities, thus promoting a clear separation of concerns.

When a user interacts with the frontend (e.g., clicking on the *quantify* button), the frontend API manager sends an HTTP request through the Axios [18] client to the backend. This request is routed to the appropriate controller in the backend based on the defined endpoint and HTTP method. The controller extracts relevant data from the request such as request body, parameters, or query strings, and subsequently forwards these data to the corresponding service files.

The service file contains the business logic of the application. Business logic refers to rules, calculations, or processes that define how data is manipulated within an application. In the case of the OpenPRA backend, business logic is of two types: executing a pre-defined function (e.g., assigning a unique JSON Web Token [19] (JWT) token after a user successfully logs in etc.) and performing operations on the MongoDB database. These operations consist of creating, fetching, updating, and deleting documents. Once the

requested functionality is executed, the results are returned to the controllers, which then relays the response back to the client.

Figure 1. Overview of the OpenPRA backend.

1.3 Heuristics for Model-Specific Optimizations

Model-specific optimizations are currently under development and will be discussed in greater detail in the final report.

1.4 Design the Parallel and Distributed Web-Based Architecture

1.4.1 Frontend Client

The frontend of the OpenPRA web app has been built using React [20] and TypeScript. React is a popular framework for frontend development that enables the creation of reusable user-interface (UI) components, improving code consistency and maintainability. The frontend client has been designed keeping these three requirements in mind:

- Collaborative environment: OpenPRA enables multiple users to work simultaneously on the same model, increasing efficiency, especially in large-scale projects involving multiple stakeholders.
- Support for a wide range of risk models: OpenPRA accommodates various risk models including event sequence diagrams, event trees, fault trees, Bayesian networks and aims to incorporate initiating event models, Markov chains, probabilistic model checking, and consequence models as well. This flexibility allows users to select the most suitable model for their specific risk analysis needs.
- User-friendly interface: OpenPRA ensures accessibility for users with varying technical expertise. The interface is designed to simplify the process of building and quantifying risk models, while also providing visualization tools to help users interpret and communicate their findings effectively.

The frontend provides secure signup, sign-in, and user profile management, ensuring that only authorized users and collaborators can access specific models. Along with security features, the frontend supports a variety of risk models through its web editor to accommodate different types of risk analysis. The web editor has been developed using Elastic UI, a design library made for React applications. The following sections provide brief overview of each risk model:

- Event Sequence Diagrams (ESDs): Supports creating ESDs, enabling compressed notation and cycles for representing complex event sequences.
- Event Trees: Graphically represents possible event sequences leading to system failure. Uses nodes and branches to depict events and their outcomes.
- Fault Trees: Models combinations of component failures that can lead to system failure, using gates (AND, OR) and basic events (component failures).

- Bayesian Networks: Represents probabilistic relationships between variables, used to model and analyze complex systems with uncertain variables.

The frontend currently includes graphical components for various risk analysis modes, each with its associated risk analysis types, allowing users to customize their risk assessment processes to fit their specific needs and preferences. However, these modes and their corresponding analysis types are still under development. Table 1 lists all the components that are currently under development. A detailed discussion about these risk analysis types and modes has been provided in Appendix A in Section 3.1 at the end of the report.

Table 1. List of risk analysis components currently under development in OpenPRA.

Analysis Modes	Analysis Types	Additional Risk Models
Internal Events Analysis	Plant Operating States Analysis Initiating Events Analysis	Initiating Events Markov Chains
Internal Hazards Analysis	Event Sequence Analysis Success Criteria Development	Probabilistic Model Checkers
External Hazards Analysis	System Analysis Human Reliability Analysis (HRA)	Consequence Models
Full Scope PRA Analysis	Mechanistic Source Term Analysis Radiological Consequence Analysis	
Data Analysis	Uncertainty Analysis Risk Integration Analysis	

Appendix A also includes several screenshots of the OpenPRA web app version 0.7.75. These images highlight the user interface and key features of OpenPRA, such as the collaborative environment, model-building interface, and results visualization tools.

1.4.2 Distributed System

A distributed system is a network of independent computers or devices that work together to achieve a common goal. The devices communicate and coordinate their actions by passing messages. Distributed systems can increase scalability, reliability, and fault tolerance. They allow resource sharing across multiple machines improving performance by sharing workloads and ensure that the system can continue to function even if some components fail.

A message broker is crucial for passing task information between these independent computers or devices. For the OpenPRA platform, RabbitMQ has been utilized as the message broker, as seen in Figure 2. RabbitMQ is an open-source tool that implements the Advanced Message Queueing Protocol (AMQP), acting as an intermediary for

messaging between applications. It enables asynchronous communication between components, provides reliable message delivery, load balancing, and data persistence. It facilitates online system monitoring as well.

Three basic concepts are necessary for understanding the mechanism of a message broker: producer, queue, and consumer. Producer is a service that converts a task or executable request into a message or job and then sends it to the broker. A queue is a buffer that stores messages. It receives messages from producers and holds them until they are consumed by one or more consumers. A consumer is an application or process that subscribes to a queue and consumes messages or jobs from that queue. The consumer extracts the tasks from these messages or jobs and executes them.

Figure 2. Overview of the distributed systems of OpenPRA

1.4.3 Implementation of the Distributed System

The distributed system for OpenPRA is being designed with a multi-priority job queue structure to efficiently manage tasks of varying computational intensities. High-priority tasks, such as uncertainty quantifications, are assigned to queues with access to more powerful worker clusters, which may include docker containers running in bare-metal or cloud servers or specialized hardware like GPUs or FPGAs. Lower-priority tasks, such as point estimate quantifications, are placed in queues with limited resources. Algorithms are under development to dynamically allocate computational resources across these queues, ensuring that no resources sit idle and that workloads are balanced across worker clusters.

In addition, model-specific optimization heuristics are being developed to improve the efficiency of the quantification process. The system will use an adaptive approach that prioritizes computations based on response time, resource availability, and desired accuracy. For example, very large event trees with hundreds of linked fault trees will be broken down into individual fault trees, which will be solved in parallel across the distributed system. After the calculations are completed, the results will be aggregated and published in a single output file. This pre-processing and post-processing strategy allows the system to handle even the most complex models efficiently, providing quick, less precise results initially and more accurate results as additional resources become available.

Finally, the system will employ a mixture of algorithms to optimize the accuracy of the quantification process. For example, it has been observed that the MOCUS algorithm tends to overestimate results when applied to scenarios with high failure probabilities. To address this, the system will use the Binary Decision Diagram (BDD) algorithm for high-probability segments and MOCUS for low-probability segments. This combination ensures that the system provides accurate results without unnecessary computational overhead, leveraging the strengths of each algorithm based on the characteristics of the model being analyzed.

1.4.4 SCRAM Quantification

The workflow of the system begins when a user presses on the *Quantify* button after developing their models in the web-editor. This interaction sends a quantification request from the frontend client to the backend server. The request contains the quantification configurations and the details of the model inside a JSON object. The model details are converted from *utf-8* to *base64* format to avoid probable parsing errors.

After receiving the request, the controller of the quantification microservice processes the request. First it validates the request body against a predefined schema using Typia [21] to make sure no erroneous or malicious requests are being sent. After successful validation it is sent to the quantification producer service. The producer serializes the JSON object into a string format to convert the request into a message and queues it on the initial job queue. RabbitMQ's role extends beyond just message queueing since it enables asynchronous processing of multiple quantification requests. Meaning, RabbitMQ allows node.js to handle hundreds or thousands of quantification requests asynchronously without halting the entire operation of the server.

The worker service consumes these messages from the job queue and parses them back to JSON objects. Then it passes each message to a certain worker cluster based on the priority level of the message. The higher the priority, the more worker clusters will be dedicated to a certain message. Each worker cluster is essentially executing the *Perform Quantification* function. This function takes in the JSON object, serializes it into a

command line string. The serialization process is straightforward for the quantification object. The model contents are converted back into *utf-8* format and stored inside temporary XML files, since SCRAM engine only accepts Open-PSA [22] Extensible Markup Language (XML) file format as inputs. The names of the XML files are then put at the end of the command line string and passed to the `scram-node-addon`. The functionality of the addon has been described in the previous section. Basically, the addon completes the quantification process and gives the result back in an XML output file. This output file is also temporarily created. The worker cluster then parses through the contents of the XML file and sends the result back to the consumer.

After receiving the result, the consumer serializes the result into a message string and sends it to the completed job queue. The `mongoose` [23] client connects to this queue, receives the message, de-serializes it into a JSON object. The `mongoose` client validates this object against a pre-defined schema and saves it as a document inside the MongoDB database after successful validation.

When the user wants to access the results, they make a GET request to the backend server through the frontend web-editor. The server receives the result and sends it back to the user. Appendix B in Section 3.2 includes a full example of the entire workflow for better visualization and understanding.

1.4.5 Quantification using Executable Binaries

In addition to the SCRAM engine, other solvers including SAPH SOLVE [24], XFTA [25], FTREX [26] etc., can also be used for the quantification of PRA models. The setup for request handling and result access methods stays the same as the SCRAM quantification process, meaning the controller, worker cluster configurations, and the storage services are the same. The only difference is the worker clusters execute the *Execute Task* method instead of the *Perform Quantification* one. In this method, the workers spawn bash terminals in the local environment of their individual docker containers. The solvers are made accessible in these terminals through command line interface (CLI) commands. For example, the command below will quantify the probability of the fault tree inside the “input1.xml” file using the MOCUS algorithm and min-cut upper bound (MCUB) approximation through the `scram-cli`.

```
1. ./scram-cli --mocus --mcub --probability input1.xml
```

Besides `scram-cli`, seven other solvers are accessible through the terminal. These are: `saphsolve`, `ftrex`, `xfta`, `xfta2`, `dpc`, `acube`, and `qrecover`. The user will pass appropriate arguments along with the name of the executable binary that they want to use for the quantification through the front-end client. Additionally, they can set the environment variables for the terminal as well. The contents will either be appended as a simple string

or else stored in temporary files and the names of the files will be added at the end of the CLI command, depending on the type of solver being used. After executing the commands, the worker clusters will return the exit code, standard output and error messages of the quantification. The standard output will essentially carry the results. If an error occurs, the standard error will be populated instead of the standard output. These output JSON objects will then be persisted in the MongoDB [27] database and can be accessed by users later.

1.4.6 Fallback Measures

There are multiple security measures placed all over the distributed system. The system incorporates several security and reliability measures to safeguard against errors, data loss, and malicious activities. Schema validation at the initial request processing stage ensures no incorrect model or malicious request is being processed. Message persistence in RabbitMQ guarantees that no requests are lost, even in unforeseen circumstances such as a broker outage. Manual acknowledgement and data persistence in MongoDB ensure that no data are lost throughout any stage of the process. Timeouts are placed at certain functionalities of the code to make sure that if a worker cluster takes too long to execute the quantification, the job will be handed over to another available worker cluster. The implementation of dead letter queue addresses the challenge of corrupted messages, preventing them from congesting the system and allowing for their safe isolation.

1.5 Algorithms for Practical Multi-Hazard Quantification

1.5.1 Demonstration of Multi-Hazard Model

All publicly available models currently include only single-hazard scenarios. To illustrate the need for such an algorithm, a set of synthetic fault tree models was created, as demonstrated in the first milestone report.

These models, detailed in Table 2, include basic events with high probabilities ranging from 0.5 to 0.9. Higher probabilities were chosen because external hazards and multi-hazard scenarios often exhibit elevated probability values. The goal is to demonstrate the importance of accurately calculating the top event's probability.

For demonstration purposes, the *ft-100* model, which includes 100 basic events along with the detailed configurations shown in Table 2 was solved using SCRAM's different algorithms and approaches for calculating probability. As seen in Table 3, the Binary Decision Diagram (BDD) solution provides exact probability results, while all other approaches, including zero-suppressed binary decision diagram (ZBDD) and MOCUS, overestimate the probability by more than seven times.

Table 2. Model generator arguments with case study configurations.

#	Argument	Options	Configurations
1	Name for fault tree	--ft-name	Autogenerated
2	Name for the root gate	--root	Root
3	Seed for PRNG	--seed	123
4	Number of basic events	--num-basic	100:50:5000
5	Average number of gate arguments	-num-args	3.0
6	Weights for gates [AND, OR, K/N, NOT, XOR]	--weights-g	[1,1,1,0,0]
7	Average percentage of common basic events per gate	--common-b	0.3
8	Average percentage of common gates per gate	--common-g	0.1
9	Average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-b	2
10	Average number of parents for common basic events	--parents-g	2
11	Number of gates	-g or -num-gate	0
12	Maximum probability of basic events	---max-prob	0.9
13	Minimum probability of basic events	--min-prob	0.5
14	Number of house events	--num-house	0
15	Number of common-cause-failure groups	--num-ccf	0
16	A file to write the fault tree	-o or -out	XML

Table 3. Comparison of different method and approaches to obtain probability and cut sets for *ft-100* model.

Method – Approach	Probability	Cut sets
MOCUS – MCUB	0.316402	676
MOCUS – REA	0.379558	676
ZBDD – REA	0.379558	676
BDD – EXACT	0.042648	676

This highlights the importance of accounting for quantification uncertainty, especially when basic events have higher probabilities, as is common in multi-hazard models. Additionally, as expected, REA results show a greater overestimation than the MCUB approach.

1.5.2 PRA Model Pre-Processor

A quantification engine-agnostic PRA model pre-processor [28] is proposed to efficiently quantify multi-hazard models, particularly those containing basic events with higher failure probabilities, which can lead to overestimation of the top event failure probability when using approximation methods like MCUB or REA. While BDD offer a more accurate solution, applying BDD to the entire PRA model may not be feasible due to its high memory requirements. Therefore, our solution selectively uses BDD for higher probabilities and employs MCUB or REA for lower probabilities. To implement this, a model pre-processor is necessary before sending models to the quantification engine.

As illustrated in Figure 3, the pre-processor operates by evaluating all input text files independently, directing solvers to either use the MOCUS MCUB method or the BDD method, depending on the probabilities involved. This approach allows for exact quantification for models with high failure probabilities, while maintaining approximate quantification for models with lower probabilities.

Figure 3. Proposed PRA model preprocessor algorithm.

The model pre-processor is written in Python and is designed to be adaptable for any quantification engine. For demonstration purposes, SCRAM and OpenPSA XML models were chosen; however, the proposed preprocessor might be extended to use for any quantification engine. The pre-processor also leverages multithreading, enabling each independent model to be solved in parallel, thereby speeding up the overall quantification process.

For demonstration, various fault tree models with identical configurations (shown in Table 2) were created, differing only in the range of maximum and minimum failure probabilities.

As observed in Table 4, pre-determined truncation thresholds and a failure probability percentage below 0.5 work effectively for the given examples. Further testing would be beneficial to extend this work in the future.

Table 4. SCRAM run results for models pass through PRA model preprocessor.

#	Configuration/Model	Percentage of Failure Probabilities Less than 0.5	Preferred Run	BDD Probability	MOCUS-MCUB Probability	MOCUS-RARE Probability	ZBDD-RARE Probability	Percentage Error $ABS(((BDD-MCUB/BDD)*100))$
1	ft_c1-P_0.01-0.05_100	100.00%	MOCUS-MCUB	7.8173E-16	7.7716E-16	7.8173E-16	7.8173E-16	0.58%
2	ft_c2-P_0.5-0.9_100	0.00%	BDD	4.2644E-02	3.1640E-01	3.7956E-01	3.7956E-01	641.96%
3	ft_c3-P_0.01-0.9_100	61.00%	MOCUS-MCUB	5.1183E-04	5.1225E-04	5.1225E-04	5.1225E-04	0.08%
4	ft_c4-P_0.05-0.9_100	58.00%	MOCUS-MCUB	7.9262E-04	8.0046E-04	8.0047E-04	8.0047E-04	0.99%
5	ft_c5-P_0.1-0.9_100	56.00%	MOCUS-MCUB	1.3343E-03	1.3921E-03	1.3922E-03	1.3922E-03	4.33%
6	ft_c6-P_0.25-0.9_100	42.00%	BDD	5.5782E-03	8.6531E-03	8.6775E-03	8.6775E-03	55.12%
7	ft_c7-P_0.35-0.9_100	30.00%	BDD	1.3228E-02	3.6564E-02	3.7181E-02	3.7181E-02	176.41%

Explanation for model names, for example, ft_c1-P_0.01-0.05_100

- Ft :fault tree
- c1 :configuration 1
- P_0.01-0.05 :basic event failure probabilities are between 0.01 and 0.05.
- 100 :number of basic event in the fault tree model.

Figure 4. Relationship between percentage of failure probabilities less than 0.5 and quantification absolute error.

Figure 4 demonstrates that as the number of basic events with failure probabilities greater than 0.5 increases, the discrepancy in the final calculated probability grows. Additionally, the pre-processor's multithreading capability significantly accelerates calculations for independent models.

The models discussed in this section are available through the repository [29].

1.6 Conclusion and Alignment to Project Goals

The development of a web-based distributed architecture for OpenPRA has been initiated and tested with various cases. This architecture not only supports the OpenPRA quantification engine, SCRAM, but also provides a flexible framework for integrating other quantification engines with minimal configuration adjustments.

This design and implementation establish the foundation of OpenPRA as a scalable, web-based, distributed PRA tool. Additionally, the importance of accurate probability quantification was demonstrated using synthetically generated models with basic events that exhibit higher probabilities, which can lead to overestimations of the top event's failure probability. This demonstration provides a basis for further research, particularly in solving models with high probability values using the BDD algorithm.

As a follow-up, an efficient method for multi-hazard model quantification is introduced by leveraging a quantification engine-agnostic PRA model pre-processor. This pre-processor enables models to be solved based on the failure probabilities of their basic events. Moreover, it offers a multithreading capability to speed up calculations for independent models.

2 References

- [1] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Benchmark Study of XFTA and SCRAM Fault Tree Solvers Using Synthetically Generated Fault Trees Models," in *Volume 9: Mechanics of Solids, Structures, and Fluids; Micro- and Nano-Systems Engineering and Packaging; Safety Engineering, Risk, and Reliability Analysis; Research Posters*, Columbus, Ohio, USA: American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Oct. 2022, p. V009T14A016. doi: 10.1115/IMECE2022-95783.
- [2] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Methodology and Demonstration for Performance Analysis of a Probabilistic Risk Assessment Quantification Engine: SCRAM," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 452–459.
- [3] E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, A. Earthperson, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Method of Developing a SCRAM Parallel Engine for Efficient Quantification of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Models," in *18th International Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Analysis (PSA 2023)*, Knoxville, TN: American Nuclear Society, 2023, pp. 134–140.
- [4] A. Earthperson, E. M. Aras, A. S. Farag, and M. A. Diaconeasa, "Introducing OpenPRA: A Web-Based Framework for Collaborative Probabilistic Risk Assessment," in *Proceedings of the ASME 2023*, New Orleans, Louisiana, USA, Oct. 2023.
- [5] A. Farag, S. Wood, A. Earthperson, E. Aras, J. Boyce, and M. Diaconeasa, "Evaluating PRA Tools for Accurate and Efficient Quantifications: A Follow-Up Benchmarking Study Including FTREX," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 573–582. doi: 10.13182/T130-43377.
- [6] E. Aras *et al.*, "Introducing OpenPRA's Quantification Engine: Exploring Capabilities, Recognizing Limitations, and Charting the Path to Enhancement," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 552–561. doi: 10.13182/T130-43362.
- [7] E. Aras, S. Wood, J. Boyce, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Enhancing the SAPHIRE Solve Engine: Initial Progress and Efforts," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 542–551. doi: 10.13182/T130-43361.
- [8] S. Wood, J. Boyce, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Advancing SAPHIRE: Transitioning from Legacy to State-of-Art Excellence," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 532–541. doi: 10.13182/T130-43357.
- [9] A. Earthperson, E. Aras, A. Farag, and M. Diaconeasa, "Towards a Deep-Learning based Heuristic for Optimal Variable Ordering in Binary Decision Diagrams to Support Fault Tree Analysis," in *Advanced Reactor Safety (ARS)*, Las Vegas, NV: American Nuclear Society, 2024, pp. 400–409. doi: 10.13182/T130-43397.
- [10] E. M. Aras and M. A. Diaconeasa, "A Critical Look at the Need for Performing Multi-Hazard Probabilistic Risk Assessment for Nuclear Power Plants," *Eng*, vol. 2, pp. 454–467, 2021.

- [11] E. M. Aras, A. S. Amin Aly Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, "Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE: Initialization of Fault Tree/Event Tree Solver," Idaho National Laboratory (INL), Idaho Falls, ID (United States), INL/RPT-23-75066-Rev000, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.2172/2203095.
- [12] A. S. Farag, "Benchmarking Study of Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools Using Synthetically Generated Fault Tree Models: SAPHISOLVE, XFTA, and SCRAM," North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2023.
- [13] E. M. Aras, "Enhancement Methodology for Probabilistic Risk Assessment Tools through Diagnostics, Optimization, and Parallel Computing," Doctor of Philosophy, North Carolina State University, Raleigh, North Carolina, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://repository.lib.ncsu.edu/items/bb05f7f5-1cff-4beb-9312-331bc94b0b95>
- [14] "Documentation | NestJS - A progressive Node.js framework," Documentation | NestJS - A progressive Node.js framework. Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://docs.nestjs.com>
- [15] "TypeScript: JavaScript With Syntax For Types." Accessed: Jun. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>
- [16] "Introduction to GraphQL | GraphQL." Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://graphql.org/learn/>
- [17] "RabbitMQ Documentation | RabbitMQ." Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/docs>
- [18] "Getting Started | Axios Docs." Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://axios-http.com/docs/intro>
- [19] auth0.com, "JWT.IO - JSON Web Tokens Introduction." Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <http://jwt.io/>
- [20] "Quick Start – React." Accessed: Sep. 26, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://react.dev/learn>
- [21] "Typia Guide Documents - Index," Typia Guide Documents. Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://typia.io>
- [22] E. Steven and R. Antoine, Eds., "Open-PSA Model Exchange Format." 2017.
- [23] "Mongoose v8.6.2: Schemas." Accessed: Sep. 25, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://mongoosejs.com/docs/guide.html>
- [24] E. M. Aras, A. S. A. A. Farag, S. T. Wood, and J. T. Boyce, "Refining Processing Engines from SAPHIRE," Idaho National Laboratory, Idaho Falls, ID, INL/RPT-23-75066, Sep. 2023.
- [25] A. B. Rauzy, *Probabilistic Safety Analysis with XFTA*. ALTARICA ASSOCIATION, 2020.
- [26] "FTREX 2.0 User Manual." Accessed: Jul. 31, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.epri.com/research/programs/061177/results/3002018234>
- [27] "MongoDB: The Developer Data Platform | MongoDB." Accessed: Jun. 23, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mongodb.com/>
- [28] "Enhancement-of-PRA-Tools / Pre-processing-Models / pra-model-pre-processor · GitLab," GitLab. Accessed: Oct. 15, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://gitlab.com/enhancement-of-pra-tools/pre-processing-models/pra-model-pre-processor>
- [29] E. Aras, A. Earthperson, and M. Diaconeasa, *Synthetic Open-PSA Models*. (Oct. 2024). Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13996371.

3 Appendices

3.1 Appendix A: Frontend Features Currently Under Development

OpenPRA will support a wide range of analysis modes. The following sections provide an overview of the supported analysis modes:

- Internal Events Analysis: Models internal events like equipment failures or operator errors to assess their impact on system reliability.
- Internal Hazards Analysis: Models hazards originating within the system, such as fires or floods, to evaluate associated risks.
- External Hazards Analysis: Supports modeling of external events like earthquakes or extreme weather, assessing their impact on system performance.
- Full Scope PRA Analysis: Models all potential risks, including internal and external events and hazards.
- Data Analysis: Imports system data, such as failure or operational data, to gain insights into system performance.

Apart from data analysis, each of the analysis modes will support the following analysis types as well:

- Plant Operating States Analysis: Focuses on analyzing different operating states of a plant or system, such as full power, low power, or shutdown.
- Initiating Events Analysis: Identifies and evaluates events that can trigger a system's transition from normal operation to a potential accident sequence.
- Event Sequence Analysis: Analyzes the sequence of events following an initiating event to assess potential pathways to system failure.
- Success Criteria Development: Defines criteria for successful system operation and assesses the likelihood of meeting these criteria under various conditions.
- System Analysis: Analyzes system performance under different conditions, including failures and hazards.

- Human Reliability Analysis (HRA): Models the impact of human errors, both active and latent, on system performance and safety.
- Mechanistic Source Term Analysis: Models the release of hazardous materials during an accident.
- Radiological Consequence Analysis: Assesses the potential radiological consequences of a nuclear accident, including the release of radioactive materials.
- Uncertainty Analysis: Analyzes uncertainties in the inputs and outputs of the risk assessment process using parametric, non-parametric, and Monte Carlo methods.
- Risk Integration Analysis: Integrates results from various analyses to provide a comprehensive risk assessment, visualized through frequency-consequence (F-C) curves.

As previously noted, OpenPRA currently supports four risk models, with plans to introduce additional models in the future. Each model is designed to address specific components of various analysis types, offering users a comprehensive toolkit for conducting thorough risk assessments tailored to their unique needs and preferences. The following sections provide a detailed overview of the future risk models:

- Initiating Events: Allows users to build initiating events using master logic diagrams (MLD) to identify potential triggers for accident sequences.
- Markov Chains: Analyzes systems with discrete states and probabilistic transitions, commonly used to assess system reliability and availability.
- Probabilistic Model Checkers: Analyzes fault propagation in cyber-physical systems using dual-graph error propagation models.
- Consequence Models: Models consequences for each event sequence, such as radiological doses or financial losses, critical for end-to-end risk evaluation.

Figure 5 through Figure 14 are screenshots captured from the OpenPRA web app. These images showcase various aspects of OpenPRA, beginning with the landing page and extending to the user interface and key features, including the collaborative environment, model-building interface, and results visualization tools.

Figure 5. Landing page of OpenPRA.

Figure 6. Internal events analysis overview.

The screenshot shows a software interface for data analysis. On the left is a sidebar titled "PARAMETER ESTIMATES" with a dropdown menu. The menu items are: SE SPECIAL EVENTS, CR COMPONENT RELIABILITY (highlighted), IE INITIATING EVENTS, UA TRAIN UA, and C CCF. On the right is a table with columns: ID, Grouping, Compon..., Compon..., Descript..., Data So..., and Failure. The table contains three rows, all with "id1" in the ID column and "Values" in the Grouping column. The other columns contain truncated text: "Air-Operate...", "AOV_FTO", "Air-Operate...", and "EPIX/RADS".

ID	Grouping	Compon...	Compon...	Descript...	Data So...	Failure
id1	Values	Air-Operate...	AOV_FTO	Air-Operate...	EPIX/RADS	
id1	Values	Air-Operate...	AOV_FTO	Air-Operate...	EPIX/RADS	
id1	Values	Air-Operate...	AOV_FTO	Air-Operate...	EPIX/RADS	

Figure 7. Data analysis overview.

Figure 8. Event sequence diagram editor.

Figure 9. Event tree editor.

Figure 10. Fault tree analysis overview.

Figure 11. Bayesian networks editor.

Figure 12. Cut sets, uncertainty using Monta Carlo sampling.

Figure 13. Importance measures calculation.

Figure 14. Time to failure cumulative distribution function with uncertainty quantification.

In this case, since there is only one fault tree, the array contains a single model. An *utf-8* representation of the model string looks as following:

```

1. <?xml version="1.0"?>
2. <opsa-mef>
3.   <define-fault-tree name="example_ft">
4.     <define-gate name="TOP">
5.       <and>
6.         <basic-event name="BE1"/>
7.         <basic-event name="BE2"/>
8.       </and>
9.     </define-gate>
10.  </define-fault-tree>
11.  <model-data>
12.    <define-basic-event name="BE1">
13.      <float value="0.1"/>
14.    </define-basic-event>
15.    <define-basic-event name="BE2">
16.      <float value="0.1"/>
17.    </define-basic-event>
18.  </model-data>
19. </opsa-mef>

```

Once the engine quantifies the model, the output result is sent back to the backend. The result is then stored in the database, allowing the user to retrieve it later. The resulting output is displayed below:

```

1. <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2. <report>
3. <information>
4. <software name="SCRAM" version="UNSET" contacts="https://openpra.org"/>
5. <time>2024-09-29T15:02:03</time>
6. <performance>
7. <calculation-time name="TOP">
8. <products>0.000139802</products>
9. <probability>5.2991e-05</probability>
10. </calculation-time>
11. </performance>
12. <calculated-quantity name="Minimal Cut Sets">
13. <calculation-method name="MOCUS">
14. <limits>
15. <product-order>20</product-order>
16. </limits>
17. </calculation-method>
18. </calculated-quantity>
19. <calculated-quantity name="Probability Analysis" definition="Quantitative analysis of
failure probability or unavailability" approximation="mcub">
20. <calculation-method name="MCUB Approximation">
21. <limits>
22. <mission-time>8760</mission-time>
23. </limits>
24. </calculation-method>

```

```
25. </calculated-quantity>
26. <model-features>
27. <gates>1</gates>
28. <basic-events>2</basic-events>
29. <fault-trees>1</fault-trees>
30. </model-features>
31. </information>
32. <results>
33. <sum-of-products name="TOP" basic-events="2" products="1" probability="0.01"
      distribution="0 1">
34. <product order="2" probability="0.01" contribution="1">
35. <basic-event name="BE1"/>
36. <basic-event name="BE2"/>
37. </product>
38. </sum-of-products>
39. </results>
40. </report>
```